

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Methyl Isopropyl Ketone by *N*-Bromoacetamide in Acidic Media

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Oxidative kinetics of methyl isopropyl ketone (MIK) in perchloric acid media in presence of mercuric acetate have been studied by using *N*-bromoacetamide (NBA) as oxidant in the temperature range 25–45°. It has been observed that the order with respect to NBA is zero while with respect to MIK and H⁺, it is unity. Zero effect of ionic strength, acetamide and mercuric acetate and negative effect of dielectric constant have been observed. A solvent isotope effect ($k_0\text{D}_2\text{O}/k_0\text{H}_2\text{O} = 1.6 - 1.9$) at 35° has been observed. A suitable mechanism consistent with the experimental results has been proposed in which it has been suggested that the mechanistic route for NBA oxidation in an acidic medium is through the enol form of the ketone. Various activation parameters have been computed and formic and isobutyric acids have been identified as the end-products of the reaction.

RECENTLY, kinetic investigations involving NBA oxidation of some primary alcohols¹, dimethyl sulphoxide² and some aliphatic ketones^{3,4} have been reported. It appears that very little attention has been paid on its mode of oxidation. However, its analogues *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS)⁵⁻⁷ and *N*-chlorosuccinimide (NCS)^{8,9} have received substantial attention on the mode of their reaction with several substances. The different mechanistic routes reported for these structurally related *N*-halogeno organic oxidants prompted us to undertake this investigation. The authors as a part of their broad programme on NBA oxidations report the kinetic oxidation of methyl isopropyl ketone by NBA in acidic media. The main aim has been to explore the mechanistic route of this particular redox process.

Experimental

E. Merck (Germany) sample of methyl isopropyl ketone (Merck), *N*-bromoacetamide (Merck-Schuchardt), acetamide (Merck) and mercuric acetate (Merck) were used. Perchloric acid (Merck) was used as a source of hydrogen ion and sodium perchlorate (Merck) for the variation of ionic strength of the medium. NBA solution was prepared always fresh and its strength was checked iodometrically. Deuterium oxide (purity 99.4%) was supplied by B.A.R.C., Bombay (India). Triple-distilled water was used throughout the investigation. The reaction stills were blackened from outside.

The reaction was initiated by rapid addition of NBA to the reaction mixture, maintained at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating unconsumed [NBA] iodometrically at different time intervals.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry of the reaction was ascertained by equilibrating the reaction mixture containing an excess of NBA over MIK at 45° for 48 h, and the estimation of unconsumed NBA in different sets showed that 1 mole of ketone consumed three moles of NBA according to the stoichiometric equation (1).

where, R is *i*-C₃H₇ group. The products, aliphatic acids were detected by conventional method¹⁰.

The oxidation of MIK by NBA studied over a wide range of concentrations of the reactant showed that the reaction follows zero order dependence on NBA (Table 1). Further, a linear increase in the zero order rate constants with an increase in the initial concentration of MIK was observed. The average values of first order rate constants k_1 ($k_1 = k_0/[\text{MIK}]$) were found to be 1.01 and $1.68 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30 and 35°, respectively. Table 2 reports the effect of [H⁺], [acetamide], ionic strength and [Hg(OAc)₂] on reaction rate. It was observed that with increasing [H⁺], the zero order rate constants in NBA increased linearly and $k_0/[\text{HClO}_4]$ had a fairly constant value. This established first order dependence of the reaction on hydrogen ion. The average values of first order rate constants were 3.54 and $5.89 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30 and 35°, respectively. Insignificant effects of acetamide, sodium perchlorate (for variation of ionic strength) and mercuric acetate additions were observed.

The NBA oxidation of MIK was also carried out in 60 and 80% D₂O; 20, 35, 50 and 60% acetic acid (v/v) and at 25, 30, 35, 40 and 45° (Table 3). Successive addition of acetic acid to the reaction

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON THE RATE

[Hg(OAc)₂] = 6.00 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 8.00 × 10⁻³ M

[NBA] × 10 ³ M	[Methyl isopropyl ketone] M	× 10 ⁷ k _o mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	
		30°	35°
0.92	5.00	2.97	5.05
1.22	5.00	2.97	4.94
1.49	5.00	2.92	5.12
1.82	5.00	2.92	4.98
2.28	5.00	2.92	4.98
2.83	5.00	2.68	5.00
3.62	5.00	2.70	5.19
4.80	5.00	2.74	4.88
0.96	1.00	1.04*	1.70*
0.96	1.70	1.80*	3.06*
0.96	2.00	2.03*	3.30*
0.96	2.50	2.22*	3.76*
0.96	3.00	3.06*	5.13*
0.96	5.00	5.02*	8.54*

* [HClO₄] = 1.60 × 10⁻¹ M and [Hg(OAc)₂] = 1.20 × 10⁻³ M.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [H⁺], [ACETAMIDE], IONIC STRENGTH (μ) AND [Hg(OAc)₂] VARIATION ON REACTION RATE

[NBA] = 0.96 × 10⁻³ M, [MIK] = 5.00 × 10⁻³ M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 1.20 × 10⁻³ M (unless otherwise stated)

[HClO ₄] × 10 ³ M	× 10 ⁷ k _o mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹		[HClO ₄] × 10 ³ M	× 10 ⁷ k _o mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	
	30°	35°		30°	35°
1.30	0.47	0.78	8.00 ^d	2.90	4.48
1.70	0.63	1.00	8.00 ^e	0.90	1.50
2.50	0.87	1.48	8.00 ^f	0.92	1.52
4.00	1.45	2.46	8.00 ^g	0.98	1.53
5.00	1.80	2.97	8.00 ^h	0.91	1.51
6.70	2.21	3.72	8.00 ⁱ	0.92	1.52
10.00	3.42	5.77	8.00 ^j	2.85	4.38
8.00	2.80	4.48	8.00 ^k	2.86	4.36
8.00 ^a	2.82	4.50	8.00 ^l	2.87	4.37
8.00 ^b	2.81	4.50	8.00 ^m	2.85	4.36
8.00 ^c	2.82	4.49	8.00 ⁿ	2.87	4.36

[Acetamide]: ^a 2.00, ^b 4.00, ^c 6.00 and ^d 8.00 × 10⁻³ M.
 Ionic strength (μ): ^e 8.48, ^f 9.00, ^g 9.60, ^h 12.00 and ⁱ 16.50 × 10⁻³ M at [MIK] = 0.2 M.
 [Hg(OAc)₂]: ^j 1.60, ^k 2.00, ^l 2.50, ^m 3.2 and ⁿ 4.00 × 10⁻³ M.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF D₂O AND ACETIC ACID ADDITIONS AND TEMPERATURE VARIATION ON REACTION RATE

[NBA] = 1.12 × 10⁻³ M, [MIK] = 5.00 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 8.00 × 10⁻³ M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 1.20 × 10⁻³ M

Temp. °C	D ₂ O-H ₂ O v/v (%)	Acetic acid-H ₂ O v/v (%)	× 10 ⁷ k _o mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	
30	0-100	0-100	2.90	5.00*
30	60-40	0-100	4.64	7.73*
30	80-20	0-100	5.51	9.40*
30	0-100	20-80	3.45	5.52*
30	0-100	35-65	4.24	7.00*
30	0-100	50-50	4.68	7.40*
30	0-100	60-40	5.15	8.24*
25	0-100	0-100	2.16	—
30	0-100	0-100	2.98	—
35	0-100	0-100	6.00	—
40	0-100	0-100	8.70	—
45	0-100	0-100	18.91	—

* Temp. = 35°.

measurements at different temperatures were utilised to compute the various rate parameters and their values obtained were 20.13 kcal mol⁻¹ (energy of activation, ΔE*), 2.51 × 10¹⁰ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ (frequency factor, A), 19.54 kcal mol⁻¹ (enthalpy of activation, ΔH*), -11.90 e.u. (entropy of activation, ΔS*) and 15.99 kcal mol⁻¹ (free energy of activation, ΔF*).

Oxonium salts are readily formed on protonation of ketones in acidic media. Oxygen, being more electronegative than carbon, facilitates larger contribution from the second resonating structure than the first,

NBA is known to exist in equilibria (3, 4) or (5, 6) and these two alternative equilibria³ are indistinguishable with the kinetic data.

or,

Thus, NBA itself, H₂OBr⁺ and protonated NBA, i.e. MeCON⁺H₂Br seem to be the possible oxidising species of NBA. It has been observed¹ that below [H⁺] = 0.2 M the reaction rate increases slowly but above this concentration a linear increase in the rate of the reaction with acidity is observed. They concluded that in absence of mineral acid HOBr (3) is likely to be the oxidising species, while in acidic media, cationic bromine (4, 6) is the oxidising species. Contrary to their observations, in absence of mineral acid the present redox reaction does not proceed hence HOBr cannot be the oxidising species in our case. Now on assuming H₂OBr⁺ of either (4) or (6) as the oxidising species, the rate expression would require negative effect of acetamide, contrary to our observed zero effect of acetamide. Hence, H₂OBr⁺ also can not be taken as the real oxidising species. Thus either NBA as such or protonated NBA may be the oxidising species.

The addition of mercuric acetate completely masks the possibility of any possible bromine oxidation which would have formed as a result of an interaction between NBA and HBr as

Br₂ is scavenged by mercuric acetate as unionised HgBr₂ and ensures that oxidation of ketone is purely through NBA.

The following two possible mechanisms are suggested by taking protonated NBA (Scheme 1) and NBA as such (Scheme 2) as the possible oxidising species. Here S represents the ketone, S' the conjugate acid and S'' the enol form of the

increased the reaction rate, indicating an ion-dipole interaction in the rate determining step. The rate

ketone.

(slow and rate determining step)

Scheme 1

Application of the steady-state treatment with the approximation $k_{-3} \gg k_4$ yields the rate law as

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBA}]}{dt} = \frac{3k_2k_1}{k_{-3}(k_{-1} + k_2)} [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+] \quad (8)$$

Scheme 2

Application of steady-state treatment yields the rate law as

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBA}]}{dt} \rightarrow = k' [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+] \quad (9)$$

where $k' = 3k'_1k_2/(k_{-1} + k_2)$

Both mechanisms proposed with protonated NBA (Scheme 1) and NBA (Scheme 2) as oxidant yield a rate law in conformity with the experimental observations. However, step (v) in Scheme 1 involving interaction between similarly charged ions, has been assumed to be fast step and this does not appear to be reasonable¹¹. It is therefore concluded that reaction actually follows the route as shown in Scheme 2. The magnitude of the solvent isotope effect supports the proposed mechanism. The higher rate value in deuterium oxide (D_2O) indicates a preequilibrium fast proton transfer with specific acid catalysed reaction¹¹. This establishes that the oxidation proceeds through the enol and not through the keto form of the methyl isopropyl ketone. The negligible influence of ionic strength and a negative dielectric effect also support the contention that enolic form of the ketone is involved in the rate determining steps (ii) and (vii).

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